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Research Article

**TO DETERMINE THE HEMATOLOGICAL CAUSES OF
HYPERBILIRUBINEMIA IN NEONATES UNDERWENT
EXCHANGE TRANSFUSION**¹Dr Muhammad Sanaullah, ²Dr Saadia Qureshi, ³Dr Junaid-ur-Rehman¹Rawalpindi Medical College, Rawalpindi²Xinjiang Medical University, China³Mohi-Ud-Din Islamic Medical College, Mirpur AJ&K

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Abstract:

Aim: The purpose of this study was to determine the incompatibility of G6PD, Rh and ABO in newborns with severe hyperbilirubinemia who underwent exchange transfusion.

Place and Duration: In the pediatrics Unit II of Jinnah hospital Lahore for one year duration from March 2019 to March 2020.

Materials and methods: Records of all (131) newborns who underwent exchange transfusion were reviewed. Data collected included age, gender, weight, total and direct bilirubin levels, direct Coombs test results, hemoglobin levels, hematocrit results and G6PD qualitative test results. Patients were divided into two groups: a normal enzyme group and a group deficient in G6PD activity. All data was analyzed by statistical tests using SPSS ver. 13.0 (Chicago, IL, USA).

Results: Out of 1970 newborns admitted for jaundice, 131 (6.6%) cases required replacement transfusion; the total number of exchange transfusions was 168. Factors requiring exchange transfusions were not identified in 51 (38.9%) newborns, while G6PD deficiency was the most common known cause of hyperbilirubinemia (43 newborns; 33%). Of the transfused patients, 93 (70.9%) were born on term, 74 (56.4%) were male, and 95% had normal body weight after birth. Most exchanges (51.1%) were carried out at the age of 2-4 days. Hemolysis was present in 11.6% of newborns with G6PD deficiency and in 11.3% of newborns with normal G6PD activity ($P = 0.981$). In patients with G6PD deficiency, the average age of onset of jaundice and exchange transfusion was 3 and 4.2 days after birth, respectively; in neonates with normal enzymes this age was 3.2 and 4.7 days after birth, respectively.

Conclusion: In this study, the most common cause of severe jaundice leading to exchange transfusion was G6PD deficiency (33%) without hemolysis.

KEYWORDS: neonatal jaundice; exchange transfusion; G6PD deficiency; haemolysis; kernicterus

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BACKGROUND:

Hyperbilirubinemia is a common problem in the neonatal period: 60% of full-term newborns and 80% of premature babies suffer from this disease during the first 3 days of life. Although neonatal jaundice is a transient condition, it occurs in 75% of neonatal returns in the first week of life¹⁻². In severe cases of jaundice, when bilirubin reaches a dangerous level, encephalopathy or kernicterus may occur. Treatment of jaundice in newborns usually begins with phototherapy. The level of bilirubin that transfusion should start on the stock exchange is controversial³⁻⁴. Current indications for transfusion are based on a balance between complications of encephalopathy formation and exchange transfusion⁵. Typical predisposing factors for severe jaundice include glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase deficiency (G6PD), ABO incompatibility, Rh incompatibility, prematurity, polycythemia, male sex, Asian race, and familial history of neonatal jaundice. Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD) is a metabolic enzyme that catalyzes the first reaction on the pentose phosphate pathway⁶⁻⁷. G6PD deficient red blood cells are more susceptible to oxidative stress destruction than normal red blood cells due to low NADPH levels. According to studies conducted in neonates in Pakistan, the incidence of severe jaundice and exchange transfusion in neonates with G6PD deficiency is three times higher than in neonates with normal enzymatic activity⁸⁻⁹. However, the mechanism of neonatal jaundice in patients with enzyme deficiency is not fully understood. Hemolysis may occur in newborns who develop jaundice with G6PD deficiency, but there are other important mechanisms, such as conjugation and hepatic clearance, that cause hemolysis. The purpose of this study was to determine incompatibility of G6PD, Rh and ABO in infants after exchange transfusion.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was performed on infants who underwent exchange transfusion were included for the study from the pediatrics Unit II of Jinnah hospital Lahore for one year duration from March 2019 to March 2020. Infants with multiple birth

defects or a history of choking were excluded. An elderly person accompanied by nurses performed the transfusion. The umbilical vein catheterization was the only method of exchange transfusion. To determine the cause or causes of jaundice, direct Coombs tests, a qualitative G6PD activity point test, and neonatal blood group (BG) and Rh tests were performed. BG and Rh mothers were also examined. Hemolysis was detected when the reticulocyte count was greater than $0.5 \pm 0.4 - 3.2 \pm 1.4\%$ and the hemoglobin was less than $14.2 \pm 2.1 \text{ g / dl} - 17.3 \pm 2.3 \text{ g / dl}$, depending on the days of the newborn. To assess sex ratio and the presence or absence of hemolysis, children were divided into two groups as normal enzymatic activity and weak enzymatic activity. We record weight, reference age, time to onset of hyper-bilirubinemia, transfusion age, and total and direct bilirubin, hemoglobin, blood group and mother and newborn Rh, direct Coombs test, morphology, GR count, reticulocyte count and quality of G6PD activity results. The consent of the parents and the institution was obtained by. To assess the significance of means between the two groups, SPSS version 18.0 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA) and Student's t-test were used. P values <0.05 were considered statistically significant.

RESULTS:

Of 1970 newborns with neonatal jaundice 131 (6.6%) required transfusions. The total number of exchange transfusions was 168. Fifty-five exchanges (32.7%) in the G6PD deficient group and 113 (67.2%) in newborns with normal enzymatic activity. The maximum number of transfusion per patient was three (carried out for 3 children); 19 newborns received two procedures. Among children with enzyme deficiency, 2 children need three transfusions, 8 children need two transfusions, and 33 children only need one transfusion. All children who have received more than one transfusion are boys. There are 12 cases of kernicterus (8 males, 4 females) at the time of admission. Unfortunately, three newborns expired, two after an exchange transfusion and before one exchange transfusion. The etiology of hyper-bilirubinemia was not found in 51 newborns (38.9%) [Table 1].

Causes	Number	Percentage
G6PD deficiency	43	32.9
ABO incompatibility	20	15.3
ABO incompatibility with G6PD deficiency	10	07.6
Rh incompatibility	05	03.8

TABLE 1: Hematologic causes of pathologic jaundice

In the neonatal period there were 93 (70.9%) and 74 male newborns (56.4%) [Table 2].

TABLE 2: Sex and gestational age distribution

Sex	Full term	Preterm	Total
Male	50	24	074
Female	43	14	057
Total	93	38	131

Assessment of the frequency of foreign exchange transfusions by birth weight showed that the majority of foreign exchange transfusions were performed in newborns with a birth weight of 2500 g [Fig. 1] Most exchange transfusions (67.51%) were performed between 2 and 4 days [Fig. 2] 42 newborns (32.8%) with G6PD deficiency; Of these, 33 (76.7%) are men and 10 (23.3%) are women. In neonates with normal enzymatic activity, 41 cases (46.5%) were men and 47 cases (53.5%) were women [Table 3].

TABLE 3: The mean total bilirubin, mean haemoglobin level, presence of haemolysis and distribution by sex in G6PD-normal and G6PD-deficient newborns

Variable	Normal G6PD (No = 88)	G6PD deficient (No = 43)	P value
Mean bilirubin	23.2 ± 7.2	21.5 ± 6.9	0.538
Mean haemoglobin	14.3 ± 4.1	16.3 ± 2.2	0.0485
Presence of haemolysis	10 (11.3%)	5 (11.6%)	0.981
Male to female ratio	0.87	3.3	0.0324

The average weight of children with enzyme deficiency was 3,050 g and 2,900 g for children with normal enzymatic activity. The maximum reported bilirubin level was 31 mg / dL in neonates with enzyme deficiency and 40 mg / dL in neonates with normal enzyme. The minimum and maximum weight of the newborn during transfusion on the stock market was 850 g and 4300 g, respectively. There was no significant difference between the two groups in terms of mean bilirubin and hemolysis (Table 3).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS:

Exchange transfusion is currently the most effective treatment for newborns with severe jaundice. Although the number of newborns requiring exchange transfusion has decreased in recent years, about 7% of newborns still need this procedure. In our study, 6.6% of neonates who had jaundice required an exchange transfusion. The differences in change relative to acceptance transfusion may be due to various causes of jaundice and delays in medical centers. The delay in applying for admission to a medical center may be due to the limited experience of general practitioners providing primary care in rural areas and incorrect information of parents about the treatment of hyperbilirubinemia. In our study, the most common cause of severe jaundice that causes exchange transfusion was 'uncertain' (38.9%); this may be due to the fact that we have limited possibilities to diagnose the causes of pathological jaundice. G6PD deficiency is a genetic disease that can be found in our city more often than in other places. However, there are no published studies in this field and this is only a hypothesis supported by daily observations. The tendency to reduce hospital stay for both mothers and infants after birth has led to an increase in readmission rates due to severe jaundice. Therefore, it should be emphasized that newborns at

risk of severe jaundice should be screened and their bilirubin levels measured prior to discharge from hospital. In this study, most transfusions (67, 51.1%) were performed 2-4 days after delivery, and the mean age of infants during exchange transfusion was 4.2 days. In our country, most newborns were discharged even 24 hours ago due to financial restrictions and insufficient support from the insurance institution. Like our findings, the Badiie study showed an average age of 4.4 days, showing early referral and transfusion changes in a timely manner in these children. In our study, 70.9% of children who underwent transfusion were born during this period. A similar discovery was reported in the Sanpavat study (72.9%). G6PD deficiency is the most common disease associated with enzyme deficiency in the world. Lack of this enzyme is a major cause of severe jaundice and can lead to cornea and death. According to a World Health Organization (WHO) report, the Islamic Republic of Iran is in an area with moderate to high prevalence of G6PD deficiency. Previous studies in Pakistan have shown that the incidence of this enzyme deficiency is higher in the north and south compared to other provinces. In this study, 33% of children after transfusion had G6PD deficiency. It was reported that the ratio of men to women was 3: 1 and 5: 1, respectively, among children with enzyme

deficiency. Inactivation of the X chromosome may cause the appearance of two groups of red blood cells in heterozygous women. In such cases, the patient's red blood cells may show normal, medium or markedly reduced enzyme activity. The need for repeat exchange transfusion in male newborns indicates a more severe enzyme deficiency in men than in women, suggesting that all hemisogic males and homozygous or heterozygous newborns have inactive X chromosomes. In this study, in 80% of cases, on the second or third day after birth, jaundice appeared in children with enzyme deficiency, and the mean age at the time of transfusion change in neonates with enzyme deficiency was normalized neonates. In addition, the lack of a G6PD umbilical cord screening test that causes an incorrect diagnosis of endangered newborns is the reason for this difference. Our findings did not differ significantly between groups in normal enzyme activity and enzyme deficiency in average bilirubin and hemoglobin levels. Ahmadi et al. Similar findings have been reported indicating that haemolysis is not the cause of jaundice in these newborns. Probably the cause of this problem is a simultaneous genetic mutation in G6PD activity and errors in the use of glucose in uredines' diphosphate. Factors that cause hemolysis in newborns with enzyme deficiency include infection, acidosis, and hypoglycemia, maternal use of oxidative drugs and / or beans, and injection of oxytocin during delivery. In our study, 11.6% of children with enzyme deficiency had symptoms of hemolysis. This discovery, Eghbalian et al. It is similar to the results obtained in the study by. However, Madan et al. This is inconsistent with the study, in which haemolysis was found in 10.9% and 41.7% of neonates with enzyme deficiency, respectively. WHO recommends the G6PD screening test for all children born in high prevalence areas (3% - 5%), including Iran. G6PD was the most common cause in stock market transfusions.

RECOMMENDATION:

G6PD was the most common hematology in neonates with exchange transfusions. Genetic mutation analysis may be appropriate to determine which type is dominant.

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